

BULLYING EXPERIENCES AND HELP-SEEKING AMONG GRADE 11 STUDENTS: A QUALITATIVE PERSPECTIVE

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Bullying Experiences and Help-Seeking among Grade 11 Students: A Qualitative Perspective

Enrique D. Laurente*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This study examines the bullying experiences and help-seeking behaviors of Grade 11 students at Aklan National High School for Arts and Trades during the academic year 2023–2024. Employing a qualitative phenomenological approach, the research involved interviews and focus group discussions with identified victims of bullying to explore their lived experiences. The findings reveal that bullying is a complex issue manifesting in verbal, physical, social, and cyber forms, occurring both within the school environment and in digital spaces beyond school hours. Participants described the emotional and psychological impacts of bullying and highlighted various coping mechanisms, ranging from personal resilience to seeking support from peers, family members, or school personnel. The study underscores the importance of understanding these experiences and behaviors to inform the development of effective anti-bullying programs and support systems in schools. By addressing the multifaceted nature of bullying and its consequences, the research offers critical insights for creating safer and more inclusive educational environments.

Keywords: *physical bullying, verbal bullying, social bullying, cyberbullying, help-seeking behaviors*

Introduction

Bullying is an issue that affects students globally, with significant effects for mental health, academic performance, and overall well-being (Hatzenbuehler & Keyes, 2013; Olweus, 2014). In the Philippine context, bullying remains a vital concern, made worse by cultural factors that may discourage open discussions about victimization and mental health (Bacalso, 2020). Defined as aggressive behavior characterized by a power imbalance and repeated over time, bullying has multiple forms, including physical, verbal, social, and cyberbullying (Shaw & Cross, 2012). Recent studies showed alarmingly high rates of bullying in the Philippines, with many students experiencing stress as a result (Bacalso, 2020; Villanueva et al., 2021).

The Anti-Bullying Act of 2013 (Republic Act No. 10627) was made to address this issue, mandating schools to place policies and programs with the purpose of preventing and addressing bullying. However, the effectiveness of these measures remains questionable, as many students continue to confide feeling unsafe and unsupported in their educational environments (Lindner, 2018). Despite extensive research on bullying prevalence and policy implementation, there is a limited understanding of the experiences of Filipino students who are victims of bullying and how they seek help.

This study addresses this gap by investigating the bullying experiences and help-seeking behaviors of Grade 11 students in the Philippines, focusing on their views and coping mechanisms. By employing a qualitative approach, the research seeks to provide nuanced insights that can inform school policies and practices to create safer and more inclusive educational environments.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the bullying experiences and help-seeking behaviors of Grade 11 Senior High School students for the academic year 2023–2024 of Aklan National High School for Arts and Trades. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the participants' bullying experience in terms of:
 - 1.1. physical bullying;
 - 1.2. verbal bullying;
 - 1.3. social bullying; and
 - 1.4. cyberbullying?
2. Why are these students being bullied at school?
3. What help-seeking behaviors did the victims pursue after they experienced bullying?

Literature Review

Bullying among students

Various studies and literature provide critical insights into its nature, prevalence, and impact. Hatzenbuehler and Keyes (2013) define bullying as socially unacceptable behavior that manifests in various ways, including physical, verbal, social, and cyberbullying. They emphasize that bullying is characterized by its repetitive nature and power imbalance, which can occur in both school environments and online platforms. Olweus, as cited in Shaw & Cross (2012), further elaborates that bullying involves aggressive behavior repeated over time, with the intent to harm the target, highlighting the significance of understanding the context in which these behaviors occur. Coffin et al. (2010) emphasize that definitions of bullying are context-dependent, shaped by cultural norms and language within communities. Their research indicates that bullying behaviors often reflect familial patterns, where children may emulate aggressive behaviors observed in their home environments. This notion is supported by Finkelhor et al. (2012), who argue that despite decades of

research, significant limitations remain in effectively addressing bullying in schools. Randa and Reys (2014) further elaborate on the evolving nature of bullying, particularly in the digital age, where cyberbullying has emerged as a significant concern. They assert that traditional definitions of bullying must adapt to include online harassment, which can occur in both school settings and digital platforms. Hemphill et al. (2012) provide descriptive information on the prevalence of bullying, identifying traditional bullying behaviors such as teasing and social exclusion as common among secondary school students.

Motivation on Bullying

Theoretical frameworks such as Humiliation Theory (Lindner, 2003) and Dominance Theory (Long & Pellegrini, 2003) provide valuable insights into the motivations behind bullying behaviors. Humiliation Theory posits that bullying leads to feelings of shame and powerlessness in victims, while Dominance Theory suggests that bullies seek to establish and maintain social hierarchies through aggressive behaviors.

Help-Seeking Behaviors

Research indicates that victims often hesitate to report bullying due to fears of disbelief or exacerbating the situation (Yablon, 2017). Blomqvist et al. (2020) found that factors such as gender, grade level, and perceived support from peers significantly influence the likelihood of victims disclosing their experiences to adults.

Methodology

Research Design

This study presented the bullying experiences and help-seeking behaviors of Grade 11 students at Aklan National High School for Arts and Trades using a qualitative methodology and a phenomenological approach of research. The phenomenological technique was used because it aims to understand the essence of experiences from the view of the people involved, which makes it appropriate for investigating the psychological and emotional effects of bullying. By using this technique, the researchers were able to examine participant tales in great detail and find recurring themes and patterns that represented their common experiences.

Respondents

The study included twelve Grade 11 Senior High School students who had been identified as bullying victims during the 2023–2024 school year participated in the study. To guarantee representation, participants included five females and seven males from five distinct class sections. Every participant said they had been a victim of verbal bullying, nine also claimed being physically bullied, four reported being socially bullied, and one reported being cyberbullied.

A questionnaire was sent to every Grade 11 student in order to choose participants. Students who reported "severe" bullying were reached out to for participation and obtained parental consent prior to being included in the study. The survey asked students to provide their name, section, and rate the severity of the bullying they experienced on a scale of "not at all," "mild," "moderate," or "severe."

Instrument

The primary instruments for data collection were in-depth personal interviews and focus group discussions. A structured interview guide was used to ensure consistency, focusing on participants' profiles, bullying experiences, and help-seeking behaviors. Nonverbal cues observed during interviews and additional document analysis enhanced the depth of the collected data. Audio recordings of the interviews were transcribed verbatim for analysis. A focus group discussion followed the individual interviews to validate findings and provide additional insights.

Procedure

The following steps were taken as part of the data collection process:

Survey: To find out which pupils in Grade 11 had experienced severe bullying, a questionnaire was given to them.

Interviews: To prevent interfering with their regular class, in-person interviews were done with participants during recess and lunch or any vacant time. A comprehensive examination of the participants' experiences and help-seeking behaviors was guaranteed by the structured interview guide.

Focus Group Discussions: To confirm the information gathered from the interviews and take into account the participants' combined perspectives, a follow-up focus group discussion was held.

Audio recording, verbatim transcription, and theme analysis coding were used for all interviews and conversations.

Thematic analysis was used to identify patterns and themes in the data. Transcriptions of interviews and focus group discussions were reviewed repeatedly, and initial codes were generated based on recurring ideas and phrases. These codes were then arranged into broader themes such as types of bullying, emotional impacts, coping mechanisms, and help-seeking behaviors. The coding process ensured that the derived themes accurately reflected participants' lived experiences, aligning with the phenomenological approach's

goal of capturing the essence of their realities.

Ethical Considerations

The ethical considerations of the study included obtaining permission from both participants and their parents or guardians before data collection. The researcher clearly communicated the study's purpose and ensured confidentiality regarding the information gathered during interviews. Participants were treated with respect and dignity, fostering a comfortable environment for sharing sensitive experiences. They were informed that participation was voluntary, and they could choose not to answer any questions they found uncomfortable. Additionally, measures were implemented to protect participants' identities and maintain anonymity throughout the research process, emphasizing a commitment to their safety and well-being.

A flow diagram (Figure 1) of the in-depth personal interview is shown on the next page, where the participants' welfare is observed, nonverbal cues are noted, and open-ended questions are asked, with follow-up questions given if needed.

Results and Discussion

The study showed that participants experienced different kinds of bullying, often simultaneously, throughout their schooling. Below are the key findings:

Forms of Bullying

Bullying is showcased in various forms, affecting victims differently. Understanding these forms helps enlighten the most common challenges faced by individuals.

Verbal Bullying: Experienced by all participants (100%), verbal bullying is observed as the most common form. Victims reported hurtful words, name-calling, and insults that left lasting emotional scars.

Physical Bullying: Reported by 75% (9 participants), physical bullying highlights its widespread occurrence. It included acts of hitting, pushing, or other physical altercation that leave victims feeling unsafe.

Social Bullying: Faced by 33.3% (4 participants), social bullying emphasizes issues of exclusion and relational aggression, where victims are deliberately isolated or excluded from social groups.

Cyberbullying: Although the least common, experienced by 8.3% (1 participant), cyberbullying still carries significant emotional weight due to its far-reaching and long-lasting effects through online platforms.

Many participants revealed being haunted by bullying experiences way back to preschool and elementary school, emphasizing the deep-rooted impact of such incidents.

Reasons for Being Bullied

The motivation behind bullying is often different and complex. Exploring these reasons provides knowledge into the triggers that lead to such harmful behaviors.

Physical Appearance (50% or 6 participants): The most frequently mentioned reason for bullying, victims experienced consistent targeting across all school levels based on their looks or body features.

Envy and Jealousy (16.67% or 2 participants): Highlighting interpersonal conflicts, envy and jealousy acted as catalysts for bullying in certain cases.

Gender Identity (8.3% or 1 participant): This reason indicates the vulnerability of marginalized identities, showcasing the unique challenges faced by individuals targeted based on their gender expression.

Unknown Causes (25% or 3 participants): Some participants were unsure of the reasons behind their victimization, suggesting deeper complexities in the dynamics of bullying behaviors.

Help-Seeking Behaviors

When confronted with bullying, victims often seek support from their immediate environment. However, the effectiveness and accessibility of these sources vary from person to person.

Friends: The most common source of support (50% or 6 participants), friends provided comfort and understanding to those experiencing bullying.

Teachers: A significant 33.3% (4 participants) turned to teachers, reflecting their role as trusted authority figures who can intervene effectively.

Siblings: Siblings were rarely approached for help (8.3% or 1 participant), highlighting potential gaps in familial support.

Dual Support: Some participants (16.67% or 2) sought help from both friends and teachers, demonstrating a combined reliance on peer

and authority support.

Non-Seeking Behavior: Alarmingly, 25% (3 participants) chose not to seek help from anyone, including parents. This highlights feelings of isolation, helplessness, and the need for better support systems.

Coping Strategies

Coping with bullying is a deeply personal process, varying based on the individual’s circumstances and available resources. These strategies reflect how victims manage their experiences.

Problem-Focused Coping: Victims actively sought solutions to mitigate bullying experiences, such as avoiding bullies or addressing conflicts directly. However, feelings of isolation often deterred them from reaching out for help, leading many to rely on internal resilience or peer support to navigate their challenges.

The findings revealed that participants experienced various forms of bullying—verbal, physical, social, and cyberbullying—often simultaneously, with lingering impacts from preschool and elementary years. Verbal bullying was the most prevalent, experienced by all participants (100%), followed by physical bullying (75%), social bullying (33.3%), and cyberbullying (8.3%). Feelings of isolation and helplessness were common, deterring many victims from seeking help. Those who did reach out often confided in friends (50%) or teachers (33.3%), while others turned to siblings (8.3%). Alarmingly, 25% of participants chose not to seek assistance at all. Coping strategies varied, with problem-focused coping being the most common. The main reasons for bullying included physical appearance (50%), envy or jealousy (16.67%), gender identity (8.3%), and unknown causes (25%). Across all schooling stages, physical appearance remained the primary target of bullying.

Figure 2 shows the Themes Developed from Participants’ Physical Bullying Experiences. this includes themes such as hitting, throwing things, locked up, pulling down pants, choking, breast squeezing. Table 1 shows the summary of patterns of physical bullying behavior revealed in participants’ interview. Figure 3 shows the themes developed from participants’ Verbal Bullying Experiences. This includes hurtful words, threat, name calling as themes. Table 2 shows the summary of patterns of verbal bullying behavior revealed in participants’ interview. Figure 4 shows the themes Developed from participants’ social bullying experiences. This includes the themes isolated and prank. Table 3 shows the summary of patterns of social bullying behavior revealed in participants’ interview. Figure 5 shows the themes developed from participants’ cyberbullying experiences. This includes group chat and Facebook wall post. Table 4 shows summary of patterns of cyberbullying behavior revealed in participant’s interview. Figure 6 shows themes developed from participants’ reasons for being bullied. This includes gender identity, physical appearance, envy, jealousy and unknown reasons. Figure 7 shows themes developed from participants’ help-seeking behaviors.

Theme	Characteristic of Responses
Hitting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They are hurting me, striking my head. • If I didn't pay attention to them, they would hurt me. They hit me just to get my attention. • Almost every month, I was punched three times. • It's like they kicked my seat. I told them that it hurt me. It also hit me. • It's like they are throwing punches. • They teased and hit me.
Throwing Things	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Sometimes they threw crumpled paper at me. • They throw at me crumpled paper when I was in 1st grade.
Locked Up	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They locked me up inside the cr. • They just locked me up. • It was hot inside. It was dark, and it was quite hard to breath. • They locked me up, but the lock got jammed, and they didn't know how to open it.
Pulling Down Pants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They pulled down my pants. • Many saw my underwear when they pulled down my pants.
Choking	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It's like they are choking you. • It's starts with a choke, but it progressed to a more physical fight.
Breast Squeezing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They would squeeze my breast. • I told them that I might get cancer from what they were doing to me.

Figure 1. Themes Developed from Participants’ Physical Bullying Experiences

Table 1. Summary of Patterns of Physical Bullying Behavior Revealed in Participants' Interview

Types of Physical Bullying	Description of incident (Action)	Reasons why?	Who do they seek help from?
Hitting	Intentionally striking the head or punching the victims' shoulder.	Unknown	Did not seek help
Throwing things	Kicking the victim's seat, which in turn hits the victim. They were throwing crumpled paper at the victim.	Unknown Physical appearance	Did not seek help
Locked up	Locking the victim in a dark, cramped comfort room, making it hard to breathe.	Unknown	Teacher
Pulling down pants	Suddenly pulling down the PE pants.	Unknown	Did not seek help
Choking	Grabbing the victim's neck in a choke-like manner.	Unknown	Did not seek help
Breast squeezing	Repeatedly squeezing the breast for several days.	Physical appearance	Did not seek help

Figure 2. Themes Developed from Participants' Verbal Bullying Experiences

Table 2. Summary of Patterns of Verbal Bullying Behavior Revealed in Participants' Interview

Types of Verbal Bullying	Description of incident (Verbatim)	Reasons why?	Who do they seek help from?
Hurtful words	You are not a straight male.	Gender identity	Friend
	You are fat.	Physical appearance	Did not seek help
	He is not losing weight.	Physical appearance	Did not seek help
	Your armpits stinks.	Physical appearance	Did not seek help
	She is naughty.	Jealousy	Sibling
	She is flirty.	Jealousy	Sibling
	You are arrogant.	Envy	Teacher
	They said my mom was fat.	Physical appearance	Did not seek help
	They said I was ugly.	Physical appearance	Did not seek help
	They said that I was a coward.	Physical appearance	Did not seek help
Threatening	You are not smart, you're not!	Envy	Did not seek help
	'You just wait for tomorrow; you'll see.' That's	Physical appearance	Did not seek help

	what he's saying to me. It feels like a threat.		
Name calling	Gorilla	Physical appearance	Did not seek help
	Ugly	Physical appearance	Did not seek help
	Pig	Physical appearance	Did not seek help
	Panot (Bald)	Physical appearance	Did not seek help
	Dwarf	Physical appearance	Did not seek help
	Turtle	Physical appearance	Did not seek help
	Weirdo	Physical appearance	Sibling
	Short	Physical appearance	Did not seek help
	Little	Physical appearance	Did not seek help
	Fat	Physical appearance	Did not seek help

Figure 3. Themes Developed from Participants' Social Bullying Experiences

Table 3. Summary of Patterns of Social Bullying Behavior Revealed in Participants' Interview

Types of Social Bullying	Description of incident (Past events)	Reasons why?	Who do they seek help from?
Isolating	They called me a fake friend and a user, and they ignored me.	Envy	Teacher
	It seems they did stay away from me.	Physical appearance	Sibling
	They don't like me to be with them.	Unknown.	Did not seek help
	Every day he felt like he didn't belong, that he always did things alone.	Envy	Teacher
Pranking	He arrived at 1 p.m. and found no one there. Later, he discovered they had played a prank on him. It was a prank.	Physical appearance	Did not seek help

Figure 4. Themes Developed from Participants' Cyberbullying Experiences

Table 4. Summary of Patterns of Cyberbullying Behavior Revealed in Participant's Interview

Types of Cyberbullying	Description of incident (Social media post)	Reasons why?	Who do they seek help from?
Group chat comments	Commenting with provocative words about a participant of this study.	Physical appearance	Did not seek help
Facebook wall post	He posted that if you ever clown around, he'd squeeze and smack you. There was a comment encouraging him to injure the participant in this study.	Physical appearance	Did not seek help

Figure 5. Themes Developed from Participants' Reasons for Being Bullied

Figure 6. *Themes Developed from Participants' Help-Seeking Behaviors*

The analysis includes the multifaceted nature of bullying, shaped by a combination of social dynamics, cultural norms, and individual characteristics. Consistent with previous studies (Hatzenbuehler et al., 2014; Lindner, 2018), the findings emphasize the detrimental effects of bullying on students' mental health and academic performance. In the Philippines, cultural factors—such as the stigma surrounding mental health and a fear of retaliation—emerge as significant barriers to seeking help (Bacalso, 2020). These cultural nuances underscore the urgent need for interventions that are contextually and culturally relevant. The reluctance of victims to report bullying is particularly alarming, suggesting a gap in the current support systems within schools. This gap calls for targeted strategies to increase awareness and provide training for educators and school staff in recognizing and effectively addressing bullying behaviors.

To address these issues, schools must implement comprehensive and evidence-based measures. A supportive school environment is critical to ensuring students feel safe reporting bullying incidents. This can be achieved by establishing peer-support programs, creating designated safe spaces where students can confidentially share concerns, and fostering a culture of open dialogue about bullying and mental health. Training programs for teachers and staff are equally important. These should focus on equipping educators with the skills to identify and address subtle bullying behaviors, overcome cultural barriers such as the stigma surrounding mental health, and foster empathetic responses to victims. Additionally, schools should enforce clear and actionable anti-bullying policies. These policies must define bullying behaviors, establish transparent reporting mechanisms, and outline specific preventive and corrective actions. Proactive initiatives, such as diversity workshops, kindness campaigns, and school-wide assessments of the social climate, can reinforce these policies and promote a more inclusive environment.

However, the study has notable limitations. The small sample size restricts the generalizability of its findings, as it may not fully capture the diversity of experiences across different schools and regions. Furthermore, the reliance on self-reported data introduces the potential for recall and social desirability biases, which could affect the accuracy of the results. Lastly, the cultural specificity of the findings limits their applicability to other contexts, as bullying behaviors and responses may differ significantly across cultures.

Future research should address these limitations by employing larger and more diverse sample sizes to better reflect the range of bullying experiences. Mixed-methods approaches that combine qualitative interviews with quantitative data collection can offer a more holistic understanding of the issue. Longitudinal studies tracking the long-term effects of bullying on mental health and academic outcomes would also be valuable. Additionally, comparative studies across cultural settings could shed light on how societal norms influence both bullying behaviors and coping mechanisms.

Conclusions

This research shows the existing literature on bullying by offering a deeper understanding of the experiences and coping strategies of Grade 11 students in the Philippines. The findings highlight the urgent need for targeted interventions and policies aimed at mitigating bullying and empowering victims within educational settings.

To translate these insights into practice, stakeholders—educators, policymakers, and community leaders—must collaborate to implement evidence-based anti-bullying programs that prioritize student well-being. These programs should include training for teachers on identifying and addressing bullying, creating peer-support systems, and promoting a school culture of respect and inclusivity.

Moreover, policymakers should establish clear guidelines for reporting and managing bullying incidents, ensuring accountability and timely resolution. Future research should examine the long-term impacts of these interventions and refine them to meet the evolving needs of students. By fostering a safer and more inclusive environment, schools can nurture resilience and empower students to thrive academically and socially.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Enrique D. Laurente

Aklan National High School for Arts and Trades
Department of Education – Philippines